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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF ADVERTISING IN THE XXI CENTURY

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Анотація. У XXI столітті жоден поважаючий себе бренд не може обійтися без реклами. В умовах всесторонньої жорсткої конкуренції сучасному виробнику потрібно не тільки надавати повну інформацію про свій продукт, але й простійно стимулювати продажі, а також формувати імідж компанії. Сьогодні практично неможливо уявити успішне функціонування будь якого бізнесу без чітко налагодженої маркетингової діяльності. В сучасних умовах функціонування ринкової економіки гостро постає питання ролі маркетингу на підприємстві. Виробники, намагаючись продати свій товар, використовують рекламу. На сьогоднішній день складно уявити життя без реклами. Де б людина не була, куди б не пішла, – реклама скрізь: в мобільному пристрої, в поштової скринці, на вулиці, в транспорті, в магазинах, по телевізору, на радіо та банерах. Реклама надовго засідає в голові, але, – опираючись на неї, власне, людина й робить свій вибір при купівлі того чи іншого товару. Власне, через наведені вище факти дана тематика є вкрай актуальною у наш час.

Сучасна реклама характеризується різноманітністю цілей і форм, здійснює великий вплив на економіку, ідеологію, культуру, соціальний клімат, освіту та інші аспекти життя суспільства. На рівні підприємства реклама все ширше торкається різних аспектів маркетингу та господарської діяльності в цілому. Необхідність виконання складних і неоднорідних функцій реклами зумовлює різноманітність учасників і комунікацій, які виникають у процесі їх взаємодії. Реклама продукції і діяльності підприємства – це найважливіша складова частина комплексу маркетингових заходів, своєрідний інформаційний вихід на споживача.

При правильній організації реклама дуже ефективна і сприяє швидкій та безперервній реалізації виробленої продукції. При цьому прискорюється повернення оборотних коштів підприємства, налагоджуються ділові контакти виробників з покупцями і споживачами продукції, попит зростає і перевищує пропозицію, – що, у

свою чергу, є об'єктивною основою розширення виробництва і підвищення ефективності господарської діяльності.

Ключові слова: реклама, маркетингові діяльності, цифрова трансформація, таргетинг, контент, SEO, SMM, веб-сайт, цифрові технології, інтернет-реклама, онлайн-комерція, контекстна реклама, медіа-реклама, ремаркетинг, тізерна реклама, PUSH-повідомлення, глобальна мережа, інтерактивність, віртуальна реальність, креативна культура, онлайн-бізнес, soft skills.

Annotation. In the 21st century, no self-respecting brand can do without advertising. In the conditions of all-round fierce competition, the modern manufacturer needs not only to provide complete information about his product, but also to easily stimulate sales, as well as to shape the image of the company.

Today, it is almost impossible to imagine the successful functioning of any business without well-established marketing activities. In the modern conditions of functioning of the market economy, the question of the role of marketing in the enterprise arises acutely. Manufacturers, trying to sell their products, use advertising. Today, it is difficult to imagine life without advertising. No matter where a person is, no matter where he goes, advertising is everywhere: in a mobile device, in a mailbox, on the street, in transport, in stores, on TV, on the radio, and on banners. Advertising stays in the head for a long time, but, based on it, a person actually makes his choice when buying this or that product. Actually, due to the above facts, this topic is extremely relevant nowadays.

Modern advertising is characterized by a variety of purposes and forms, exerts a great influence on the economy, ideology, culture, social climate, education and other aspects of society. At the enterprise level, advertising increasingly affects various aspects of marketing and economic activity in general. The need to perform complex and heterogeneous functions of advertising determines the diversity of participants and communications that arise in the process of their interaction. Advertising of the company's products and activities is the most important component of the complex of marketing activities, a kind of information outlet for the consumer.

With proper organization, advertising is very effective and contributes to the quick and smooth sale of manufactured products. At the same time, the return of working capital of the enterprise is accelerated, business contacts of producers with buyers and consumers of products are established, demand increases and exceeds supply – which, in turn, is the objective basis for expanding production and improving the efficiency of economic activity.

Keywords: advertising, marketing activities, digitization, targeting, content, SEO, SMM, website, digital technologies, internet advertising, online commerce, contextual advertising, media advertising, remarketing, teaser advertising, PUSH-messages, global network, interactivity, virtual reality, creative culture, online business, soft skills.

Introduction

The language of advertising is the language of the subconscious. Direct appeal to the mind of the consumer works not only in advertising of food and industrial products. Advertising has repeatedly become the object of linguistic research. A number of works devoted to structural, semantic, genre, stylistic and communicative features of advertising language and text have been performed.

Many scientists were involved in the study and analysis of this topic, including K. Aksenova, V. Babina, F. Batskevich, Yu Bondar, V. Dobrovolska, O. Donchenko, A. Dunets, H. Yepifantseva, R. Ivanchenko, O. Majeovsky, A. Marovdi, E. Romat, M. Senchenko, Ya. Terlyak, R. Kharytonyuk, and many others. This topic is quite popular, so it attracts the attention of many researchers. Although there are many

studies on this topic, a number of issues remain unresolved, the main ones being the impact of advertising on consumer choice and advertising as a special tool in the marketing system.

The purpose of the article. The purpose of the research of this article is to highlight the basics of the origin of advertising and advertising activities both in the world and in Ukraine in particular; study of the impact of advertising of various types on consumer demand and choice; analysis of the effectiveness of advertising activities in Ukraine after the full-scale offensive of the occupiers and the start of hostilities; prospect research.

Results

The modern world is woven from many advertising messages – on the phone, on the street, in transport, in a store, on radio or TV. We live in a world of total advertising, which has become an integral part of our modern life. Today, not only products need advertising, but also institutions and even individuals.

Today, advertising plays an important role in business and society – it is one of the forms of mass communication. It conveys various types of information aimed at achieving understanding between sellers and buyers. Performing a social role, advertising informs about new or better products and teaches how to use them, helps compare products and their features, giving the buyer the opportunity to make an informed purchase decision, and also reflects trends in fashion and design and contributes to aesthetic ideas citizens.

For some, advertising can even become a textbook for life, because they tell us what medicines to take, what gifts to give, what products to buy and who to vote for.

The main actors of advertising activity are advertisers, advertising agencies, mass media, intermediary service organizations and consumers of advertising. Any advertiser ordering advertising sets the goal of increasing product sales, changing consumer behavior in relation to the advertised product, and increasing knowledge about the brand under which the product is manufactured [8]. Regarding advertising ethics, advertising should be objective, informative and neutral. Today, advertising can undoubtedly be called the art of the 21st century.

The modern concept of «advertising» acts as a new substance of relations in society and raises the relationship with the consumer to a qualitatively new level. Historically developed functions are expanded, new ones are added. Advertising creates an anticipation of shopping pleasure; creates an image of the product that meets the expectations of the consumer; encourages the consumer to buy [3].

The history of the origin and development of advertising dates back several millennia. During this time, the types of advertising, methods and areas of its use have completely changed. The requirements applied to advertising have also changed. The shortcomings of the advertised products are also leveled out due to the advertising of their lower cost and other tricks. Currently, any advertising activity must adhere to several equally important principles:

- attract the attention of customers by all available means (pictures, videos, etc.);
- when submitting information, emphasize the profitability of this offer;
- influence not only directly, but also at the associative level;
- highlight the advantages of the service, thereby emphasizing that quality and service are no less important than affordability;
- it is possible to inform about: where, when and at what price the product can be purchased, saving the client's time.
- prompt action by giving a signal why you need to buy quickly, right here and exactly this product.

In the conditions of the transformation of the domestic economic system in the direction of the market model of management with the emergence and formation of small and medium-sized enterprises, Ukrainian scientists, economists, statisticians and marketers faced the question of the formation of new

approaches in the organization of advertising activities. Advertising activity contributes to the satisfaction of one of the most urgent needs – the integration of Ukraine into the European Union [2].

Economic and social transformations in Ukraine are aimed at solving complex problems of increasing the efficiency of the economy, the transition to socially oriented market relations. Solving these problems requires working out the system of theoretical and practical problems of development of forms of ownership and management, denationalization and privatization, self-management and entrepreneurship, formation of market infrastructure, development of marketing and advertising activities [6].

Translated from Latin, advertising means «to call out», «to call», that is, to popularize goods and services with the help of mass media. As advertising affects the consumer and society, so society affects advertising. In marketing, there are five factors influencing advertising as a phenomenon: economic, social, political, cultural and moral.

Advertising is considered one of the most ancient forms of economic formation. It is safe to say that advertising in its history goes back to the distant past: various forms of advertising expression are found even before our era.

The papyri of the Egyptians, discovered by archaeologists, testify to this more than clearly. The trademark of the first craftsman, the shouts of heralds or a colorful sign are edible, which is nothing but information that promotes the promotion of a product or service, that is, a form of advertising.

The oral form of advertising is mentioned in the 14th-15th century before Christmas. Ancient merchants announced their goods by shouting various slogans. Subsequently, an institute of heralds emerged, which was registered at the state level. A herald was considered a person who was hired by a merchant to call on buyers and praise the goods. Heralds first appeared among the ancient Egyptians, later among the Greeks and Romans.

The market of the Middle Ages was bright and multi-voiced: fairs, call-outs, signboards, artisans' guild festivals – these are just a few of the things that come to mind first when you think about the development of advertising.

With the development of writing (VI-VIII centuries before Christ), written advertising appeared, which was initiated in Middle Eastern cultures. It is known from many literary sources that one of the earliest advertising texts was an inscription on the ruins of Memphis: «I, Rhino of the island of Crete, by the grace of the gods interpret dreams» Samples of ancient graffiti are found on the walls of buildings in the ancient city of Pompeii. Much later, for advertising information, walls were specially whitewashed or boards covered with white paint were displayed, where important state news, government orders and other important information at that time were written.

So, the fact is undeniable that in the ancient period, oral, artistic and written forms of advertising already existed. Ancient culture is an excellent example of the development of advertising, so it is safe to say that the formation and development of advertising began long before the appearance of printing.

According to historians, the period of the 5th-10th centuries AD is a period of stagnation for advertising, since in this period (the period of the Middle Ages) the circulation of goods took place mainly within the boundaries of feudal communities, so there was no clearly expressed need for advertising.

The development of production and technical achievements have led to the fact that advertising from an additional touch, which is necessary for an idea of the life of a person at one or another stage of development, has become a bright phenomenon of modern life

It was only in the 11th century that the institute of heraldry resumed its activity in France. Heralds were needed by the royal power, clergy, knighthood and merchant guilds. In the 13th century, the first collection «One hundred and seven cries that are shouted daily in Paris» was published, in 1608 – the collection «Cries of London».

A new era in advertising activity was the invention of paper and the printing press in 1450 in Germany by J. Gutenberg. During the second half of the 15th century, printing enterprises spread throughout Europe: in 1465, the first printing press began to work in Italy, in 1468 – in Switzerland, in

1470 – in France, in 1473 – in Belgium, Hungary and Poland, in 1476 – in England, the Czech Republic and other European countries.

The first printed advertisement appeared in London in 1472 – it was an announcement on the door of a church for the sale of a prayer book. At this time, advertising continues to develop rapidly all over the world. In 1622 in England, and in 1631 in France, the first weekly newspapers and the first advertisements appeared. The emergence of new editions leads to competition between them and the need to protect their products, so the first trademarks and trademarks appear.

The first advertising agency in the world was the bureau of Arthur Gorge and Walter Kohn, which was founded in 1611 in England. In 1629, Theophrastus Renaud founded a similar agency in France. More mass advertising agencies appeared in England (1799), the USA (1828), and Germany (1855). The first advertising agencies provided only a certain range of services, agencies with a full cycle of services appeared at the end of the 19th century.

Outdoor advertising of that time is represented by signs and posters. In 1688, printed posters appeared, in particular, the first poster stands were built in England. At the end of the 19th century glass posters, later illuminated posters, began to be used in advertising.

The development of technical progress opens up new forms of advertising. In 1904, Louis Lumière filmed the first commercial promoting champagne wines.

With the development of society, advertising also developed, there was a need for catalogs, prospectuses, brochures, and direct mail advertising began to be actively used.

In the 20th century, outdoor advertising moved at a fast pace, confidently and cheerfully. The flagship of development was the USA, followed by Western Europe.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, a scientific approach gradually began to penetrate advertising. John Keplés and Claude Hopkins for the first time propose to create advertising as a combination of art and science. Attention is focused on the fact that advertising should achieve marketing goals, solve marketing tasks, and not just be beautiful or creative. In the 1930s and 1940s, specialized organizations were created to study the effectiveness of advertising. In addition, states tried to increase the aesthetics and artistic value of outdoor advertising. For example, art schools were created in Germany, which were supposed to train specialists in this direction.

Improves outdoor advertising using analog photomontage. The necessary fragments were cut out of the photos, adjusted to the required scale using magnification, glued, retouched – and reshot. Photomontage made it possible to easily create the most diverse, previously impossible, combinations of images and photos. In the 1920s, «illuminated advertising» appeared – in the evening or at night, advertising posters were illuminated by spotlights.

After the Second World War, the world saw a sharp increase in production, the development of markets, and the intensification of competition in them. Advertising, including outdoor advertising, had to be created at a new technological level in order to be ready for new challenges. Professionals from various fields are involved to increase its effectiveness: psychologists, marketers, economists. When creating advertising, they began to pay more attention to how a potential consumer will react to it, to study his behavior, perception, the impact of advertising on him.

Since the 1950s, two solid competitors have been established in outdoor advertising – television advertising and radio advertising. The improvement of outdoor advertising itself until the mid-70s followed the path of modernization of printing techniques and technologies, introduction of new modern materials. Trolls, brand walls, city lights, backlights, brand walls – the description of outdoor advertising at this time is more similar to the list of services of a modern advertising printing house.

If you take a tour of Ukrainian advertising, merchants already used the services of heralds in the days of Kyivan Rus.

With the invention of the printing press and the opening of printing houses (1578, Lviv), the trademark of Ukrainian publishers adorned many books of that time. As a result of the annexation of part

of Ukraine to Russia (1654), and part to the Austro-Hungarian Empire, Ukrainian advertising is subject to the requirements of these states.

Historically, it happened that for Ukraine, the 90s were the beginning of the assimilation of developed Western traditions in the field of advertising. Due to socio-political and economic factors, the country actually did not have its own advertising traditions at that time. The advertising space was dominated by foreign products, and their list was quite narrow compared to what Ukrainian people can see now.

An important factor was the psychological factor, i.e. consumers' attitude towards advertising. Ukrainian society turned out to be, on the one hand, not ready for the flow of advertising information that was directed at it, so it perceived advertising rather biasedly. On the other hand, consumers who were not used to advertising were undemanding to its quality. Therefore, almost any advertising product, created according to the general principles of competent construction, was potentially effective and made the expected impression [3].

With this in mind, there was no need for advertising creators back then to look for non-standard methods of attracting attention, as they do now. In addition, the domestic consumer has not yet developed a critical and selective attitude towards advertising information, characteristic of a modern person.

It should also be emphasized that for a long time there was not enough well-thought-out and prescribed legislation in the advertising sphere, therefore there were not so many current prohibitions.

Television then became an important way of consuming information. Since the Internet was not yet a mass phenomenon, television played the role of the main platform for broadcasting visual information, including advertising [7].

Due to the low competitiveness of domestic goods in the 1990s, foreign advertisers played a leading role in the Ukrainian advertising market. They did not study the peculiarities of Ukrainian consumers, did not tie their campaigns to Ukrainian culture, mentality and lifestyle. Thus, Ukrainian society was then shown a foreign way of life, moral and material values of another culture.

In the post-Soviet society, advertising became a unique socio-psychological phenomenon, because it actually formed a new economic consciousness. At that time, advertising performed several functions for the consumer: it promoted the sale of goods or services and showed the new post-Soviet reality, and also shaped consumer behavior and explained the essence of innovations.

Characteristic features of foreign advertising were bright slogans and plots, laughter, fun, songs.

They mainly advertised drinks, candies, chewing gum, etc. Popular advertised products were Yupi and Invite powders for making sweet drinks, as well as Gallina Blanca and Maggi bouillon cubes. Since the financial situation of most people in the 90s did not allow cooking soups with real meat, these cubes were wildly popular.

In the 1990s, the credibility of advertising was greatly undermined by massive advertising campaigns of investment funds that turned out to be fraudulent financial pyramids. And it is difficult not to mention the cult PR work, which really had a powerful impact – advertising of JSC «MMM». Any marketer dreams of placing his advertising so firmly in the minds of people.

Many domestic enterprises at the dawn of independence were not ready to advertise anything at all – then the first priority was to get the product. Many consumer goods did not need advertising – they were simply not available in stores. And if they did appear, they were bought up instantly without any advertising. Interestingly, they advertised mainly those products that were beyond the reach of the majority of the population at that time. Because it was their producers who had money for better advertising.

Domestic television advertising initially had a rather sad appearance. Ukrainian advertisers of those times did not actually know how to make high-quality special effects, and had not heard such words as visual and post-production. All domestic advertising was created by trial and error.

The formation of the advertising market in the country is closely related to the formation of market relations. With the appearance of more and more goods and services, people have freedom of choice in

their purchase. As a result, competition began to arise between manufacturers. And where there is competition, there is an urgent need for quality advertising.

In general, advertising in the 90s in Ukraine is a unique social and psychological phenomenon. At different periods of its development, it has experienced tremendous changes and has developed from its initial immature state to the modern level of the advertising industry.

Observing the development of advertising both domestically and in the world as a whole, we can say with confidence that advertising is a constant companion of a person and, regardless of his desire, affects his behavior, lifestyle, and value concepts. Considering the above, it is difficult to say unequivocally whether advertising is a science or an art.

The task of advertising is to create a good attitude towards the product or brand. But some scientists and specialists assure that advertising, which dislike can also be effective.

Advertising, on the one hand, conveys to the consumer the information necessary for the purchase and use of goods. On the other hand, combining your informativeness with persuasiveness and suggestion, makes a person social, emotional and psychological impact.

In the structure of social and psychological. There are three types of effects of advertising on the consumer directions:

1. Cognitive (related to how advertising perceived by a person. This direction includes analysis of such processes as: memory, sensation, perception, representation);
2. Emotional (determines an emotional attitude towards advertising information);
3. Behavioral (analysis of consumer actions under by the action of advertising) [7].

In order to encourage a person to purchase a certain product (which is what advertising does), motive alone is not enough: the product must have certain other qualities. There are different approaches to correlating one's desires with the need to buy in different strata of society based on the level of well-being.

The economic role of advertising is determined by the chain of relations between business entities, producers and consumers of products. As a result of the interaction of these subjects, business activity increases, capital investments and the number of jobs increase. Advertising promotes healthy competition, brings information about new products and services to the consumer. With the help of advertising, sales markets expand, capital circulation accelerates, as a result of which the efficiency of social production as a whole increases [4].

New opportunities for advertising are opening up in connection with the internationalization of the mass media industries. Satellite and cable television, computer networks are becoming international, new newspapers, magazines, radio and TV channels are appearing that have international popularity – all this creates favorable conditions for customers of advertising in the mass media and for the activities of advertising agencies, which select appropriate advertising media. Thus, in modern conditions, advertising becomes transnational, and advertising companies become international [1].

The end of the 20th century marked the beginning of the era of digital technologies, which significantly influenced the development of advertising activities, created new opportunities for creating and placing advertising texts. One of the most promising places for advertising has become the «world wide web» Internet. New technologies contributed to the evolution of outdoor advertising. In addition to traditional posters, huge LED monitors began to be placed on the streets of large cities.

Advertising of the 21st century, both externally and internally, is very different from the advertising messages of our predecessors. In its development, advertising activity has undergone a process of evolution together with all of humanity. In fact, even rock paintings and ritual dances of primitive man can be considered primitive advertising – emphasizing one's own superiority, i.e. – self-promotion. But, as information about the product, advertising manifested itself only when commodity-monetary relations arose.

The information age fundamentally transformed the world of marketing and advertising. The Internet has caused a lot of damage to print advertising, TV advertising, radio advertising, but outdoor advertising has not lost its relevance at all. Along with Internet advertising, outdoor advertising is challenging for

leadership at the beginning of the 21st century. These two mediums complement each other harmoniously when it comes to offline and online campaigns. The information age has given outdoor advertising a lot of new effective tools. Yes, photomontage has become digital. Cutting, gluing, retouching – all this seems like a ridiculously long process, although less than a hundred years have passed when such a process was considered an innovation. With the help of Corel Photo-Paint, GIMP, Adobe Photoshop programs, any manipulations with the footage are possible.

The creation of outdoor advertising today is preceded by the process of marketing analysis, development of marketing strategies and tactics. Collection and processing of marketing information is unthinkable without appropriate software. And the very process of creating modern outdoor advertising is literally permeated with information technologies. Experts predict that outdoor advertising in the near future will become «intelligent», will be adapted to each specific consumer, and will show the information he needs. But this is a completely different story...

Outdoor advertising is one of the oldest types of product promotion, but constant improvements in technology and changes in consumer awareness are forcing advertisers to change their strategies. Focusing on global trends in the advertising industry, demand for certain types of products, advertising companies offer something more effective and new in outdoor advertising [5].

Today's consumers need to be able to engage, because they are more informed than before, and a simple message on a monitor may not be enough. Website design, SEO technologies and the creation of various content are only a small part of the modern realities of advertisers, since the influence of outdoor advertising on its viewers occurs at different levels and you need to know all the subtleties of this area.

There is an opinion that outdoor advertising is an outdated way of providing the necessary information to a potential client, but this is not so. Income from this species has grown in recent years and continues to grow [8].

Digital marketing has also influenced street advertising. Every year we witness an increasing rejection of traditional banner designs and increasingly see digital, modern external media on our streets.

Innovations in outdoor advertising do not do without high technologies, they allow tracking the target audience, thus ensuring more effective promotion of goods and services. In the future, sensors and special software for identification will be involved. Advertisers make the necessary adjustments for maximum adaptation of the information provided to the needs of a given place, which significantly increases the chances of a consumer response. Creating high-quality advertising requires creativity, and outdoor advertising is best suited for this. Non-standard extenders, billboards, various illuminated signs open wide opportunities for the implementation of your plans.

Modern trends in advertising are diverse and aim at one thing – effective interaction with the consumer, increasing his perception and providing the necessary information. Knowing what effective outdoor advertising should be, you can form the right approach to business organization, feel the contact points and get the desired result as soon as possible.

Advertising is an important part of any business and the driving force of trade. A product or service won't sell if buyers don't know about it. In today's world, when choosing a platform for advertising, special attention should be paid to the Internet, which is regularly replenished with new users and is becoming more and more convenient for advertisers. We can even confidently say that today the Internet has become the most effective way of selling goods and services [6].

With the help of Internet advertising, you can place materials in various formats: banners, graphics, texts, videos, etc. For this, there is a certain set of tools, the choice of which should depend on the capabilities and goals of the manufacturer.

It should be noted the main advantages of advertising on the Internet:

- every minute the number of network users increases;
- the time spent by people on the Internet increases;
- online trade replaces ordinary stores and offers greater opportunities;

- mass media are also moving online en masse;
- advertising campaign management tools are progressing, the possibilities of their analysis and effectiveness measurement are improving;
- unlike classic advertising, users participate in many processes (interactivity);
- the possibility of targeting is the actual promotion of goods and services only to interested users (target audience);
- tracking the effectiveness of advertising – the manufacturer will be able to track all user actions, which will make it possible to quickly react and change the advertising campaign [1].

In general, Internet advertising makes it possible to divide users according to many characteristics: place of residence, age, gender, interests, stage of purchase.

There are several main types of advertising on the Internet, namely:

Contextual advertising (advertising in Google or Yandex) is the most convenient and effective way of advertising, with the help of which you can achieve good results with small financial investments.

The principle of contextual advertising is as follows: the user enters a query into the search engine (Google or Yandex) and receives advertisements at the top and bottom of the search results pages that correspond to the topic of the query. Or another option: the user sees ads on partner sites of the advertising network that correspond to the topic of the site itself or the history of his queries in the search engine.

Media (banner) advertising. A banner is an image that is shown to users on the partner sites of an advertising network. They can be interactive (gifs) and have different formats and sizes. They are mainly used to increase the recognition of a brand, product, or service, to form certain associations and images, and to encourage a certain action [5].

The cost of banner advertising is formed depending on:

- rating of the partner site;
- banner sizes;
- placing a banner on the page.

The fee is charged for the number of impressions or clicks on the banner.

Merchant Center is a Google service for advertising products of online stores. You will be able to upload information about them (photo, name, prices) and it will be displayed as a contextual advertisement during a search. This service can be integrated with other tools of the Google company, which will make it possible to view the statistics of products and campaigns.

Advantages of Google Merchant Center:

- convenient product lists;
- the possibility of linking to Google AdWords and Google Analytics;
- the more product views – the higher the chance to get the best place for placement;
- direct links to product cards;
- the ability to configure the georeference of buyers.

Remarketing or retargeting. Remarketing is a tactic in Internet marketing that helps to convince the user to return to the site and complete the target action (purchase, registration, subscription, filling out a form).

Advantages of remarketing:

- targeting «warmed-up» customers who have already visited your site;
- high conversion rate;
- quick return of monetary investments and reduction of the cost of attracting a buyer;
- targeting based on geographical location of users;
- the possibility of segmentation of potential buyers depending on the action, interests, prices, etc.;
- compliance of announcements of user actions;

- improvement of brand recognition.

Video advertising on Youtube. Youtube is a very popular resource on which users from all over the world upload their videos. Some of them have an impressive number of views (millions!). By advertising in videos on YouTube, you can reach a wide audience and attract a lot of customers [4].

Advantages of YouTube advertising:

- own video clip on someone else's channel (own or someone else's);
- embedded commercials on other people's videos;
- text ads on videos;
- links to videos above the search results.

In YouTube, you can also configure the display of commercials only to the target audience.

Disadvantages of YouTube advertising:

- placement on popular channels is not cheap;
- users can turn off advertising, and in paid accounts it is not shown at all;
- ads that interfere with watching a video, annoy users.

Teaser advertisement. A teaser is, like a banner, a static or animated image placed on partner sites. However, the teaser never advertises directly – it intrigues users with some kind of bait in order to click on it. Although this type of advertising does not have a very good reputation, it still has its audience.

Advertising in social networks (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok). No less popular is advertising in social networks, in which users spend a lot of time.

Almost all users registered in social networks fill out their profile with information about age, gender, interests, place of residence, etc. This makes it possible to customize the display of advertisements to interested users [4].

Advantages of advertising in social networks:

- placing advertisements for free directly on your own page;
- the possibility of creating a group or community;
- the possibility to exchange posts with another group or community;
- paid advertisement placement;
- the possibility of holding contests, promotions, bonuses;
- buyers do not need to go to another resource to make a purchase;
- availability of likes, reposts, comments;
- simplicity and convenience of placement.

Facebook has a financially secure public, so you can advertise not cheap goods/services there. It requires a thoughtful approach. It will be more effective to promote groups and communities, and then advertise your products on them, or set up targeted Facebook advertising.

Instagram specializes mainly in pictures and short videos. Promotion on Instagram comes down to receiving likes and comments on posts. Targeted advertising is also available here, which can be set up from your Facebook advertising profile [4].

Email mailings. Many Internet users still use electronic mailboxes, so advertising through email newsletters does not lose its relevance. This type of advertising is equally good for increasing sales of both goods and services. If the user leaves his email, you will be able to send him various information about: promotions, discounts, contests, product range updates, personal bonuses, etc.

PUSH messages are pop-up short messages that inform subscribers on personal computers and mobile devices about news or changes on the advertiser's website. Such messages facilitate the return of users to the site they previously visited.

Previously, they were used by software developers to remind users about updating programs or antiviruses, and social networks – to inform users about new posts and actions of friends. The principle of their operation is as follows: the user subscribes to the newsletter and then receives short information in the

form of PUSH messages. To subscribe, just click on the «Accept» button in the browser's service window [5].

Therefore, placing advertisements on the Internet is the most popular and most effective method of promoting various types of goods and services. There is a wide variety of types of advertising that have different costs and effectiveness. But, in any case, Internet advertising, if properly configured, will provide a flow of buyers and sales growth for any seller.

Yes, we all understand that the use of advertising on the global Internet is an undeniable trend in the product sales system, but we should not forget about the realities of today in Ukraine.

What can be said here. War. It seems that one small word consisting of a few letters, which completely destroys your universe, which erases all the principles and memories that were «before», which completely changes priorities, which radically changes life... or even worse – takes it away... by thousands...

Forgive our dear fellow scientists for deviating from the main topic of our research – but these are the realities of our lives, and we have been in Ukraine since the first day of the Russian Federation's offensive and until now. Therefore, we can provide comprehensive information on marketing research of the advertising market of our country.

The war in our native Ukraine has been going on for almost a year now. The country's economy and business simply «fell asleep» for almost half a year, ceasing to function. All production and all processes that ensured a healthy existence and viability of the country were frozen. People forgot about advertising, because on the front pages of all mass media, without exception, there was only one thing – the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation on the territory of Ukraine, missile strikes on the main cities, the number of injured and dead, as well as the daily appeals of the President of Ukraine to all civilized nations and nations regarding military aid to our state.

Yes, it was very difficult. And now it's hard too. But, Ukrainians are such people who are not so easily intimidated and broken – who do not give up so easily! We defend and protect our own. This is the land of our ancestors, which gives us strength and inspiration, which lifts us up and charges us with courage and will. And we will never give it to anyone. Between shelling, air strikes, sabotage and power outages throughout the territory of Ukraine, our people restored almost all production processes in the country. This also applies to the marketing activities of entrepreneurs. Of course, the situation has changed significantly, so at the moment, according to the conducted surveys, we have the following data (fig. 1.):

Figure 1. The results of a survey of respondents regarding the use of the most popular types of advertising in 2022

Source: Indicators calculated based on data from All-Ukrainian Advertising Coalition (VRK)

Internet advertising suffered the least losses, it was used by 71% of surveyed companies after 02/24/22. The biggest losses are advertising on television and in cinemas, where the number of advertisers has decreased more than 3 times for TV and 6 times for cinemas. 21% of respondents did not advertise at all after 02/24/22. Not only the number of advertisers decreased, but also the frequency of contact with consumers in each of the channels.

Marketers lack information about the consumer and the market, because the number of companies that used research in the new conditions of martial law fell by 2 times. Companies that have not abandoned research mostly talk about a decrease in the number of research projects compared to the previous year. Marketers say much more research is needed on consumer behavior, demographics due to migration, media consumption, brand health and retail audits.

Overall, only 5% of companies increased their consumer and market research this year. Every 6th company talks about reducing the staff of the marketing department, on average by 30%. However, almost every 10th company increased the number of marketing teams by 20%. Currently, the average size of the marketing department is 14 employees. 8 out of 10 advertising companies say that marketing activity has dropped significantly because of the war. Among the marketing activities planned before the war, 45% of the projects were cancelled (fig. 2.).

Figure 2. Indicators of marketing activity of enterprises in Ukraine for the first half of 2022
Source: Figure reproduced based on the authors' own research

Media advertising has undergone the greatest transformations due to the war – 7 out of 10 advertising companies talk about significant changes in this direction.

According to research, since April 2022, in terms of video length, consumers of advertising messages preferred videos of 11-15 seconds, as well as six-second ads that the user cannot miss on YouTube (fig. 3.).

Figure 3. Average length of commercials preferred by consumers in mid-2022
Source: Indicators calculated based on data from Digital Advertising Agency

Although the same tasks remain before marketing – promotion, attraction and retention of the company's users, there is a tendency to change the key indicators of work efficiency: reducing the requirements for quantitative indicators and a guideline for keeping the current number of customers.

To respond to modern challenges, marketing has to focus more on analytics and timely response, and change almost everything: communication strategies, product portfolio, pricing strategies, marketing budgets, work with partners and contractors.

The general cohesion of the business is also growing, which leads to the emergence of a wide variety of partnerships and collaborations: with competitors, with Ukrainian artists, with stars, with funds and brands to collect funds, transfers to the Armed Forces and TRO, to supply the market with goods, to create new products to meet the needs army and population, etc.

The main challenges of the future, which the interviewed companies talk about, relate to:

1. the consumer – how the consumer has changed, what and how to tell him;
2. business management – effective use of budgets, quick response to changes and forecasting in war conditions, team preservation;
3. product – optimization of brand portfolio, search for new niches and minimization of production costs, establishment of lost logistics connections and relocation or restoration of destroyed production facilities.

Experts believe that the main theme of the future is reconstruction. They also point out the importance of other topics – the price of victory, our psycho-emotional state, rejection of old partners, change of mood and support of «our Ukrainian». Given the changes that will take place in society, brand communication must take into account new needs and new target audiences (fig. 4.).

Figure 4. The main trends in advertising activities in Ukraine for the last half of 2022

Source: Figure reproduced based on the authors' own research

Therefore, despite the difficult state in which the country and the advertising industry in particular found themselves, most advertising companies are reformatting their business processes and marketing functions, updating communication strategies and starting to allocate budgets for marketing activities.

The advertising market is struggling – literally and figuratively. As far as we know, most agencies participate in information resistance campaigns, creation of propaganda materials for Ukrainian ministries and volunteer organizations. There has never been such an overall performance, perhaps never. In this sense, the market is definitely alive and fighting.

Conclusion

The digitalization process is progressing every day allowed manufacturers and sellers for the first time to get so close to the consumer is out of the question sales points and achieve coverage without additional costs. However, in order for this proximity continued to give results, the involvement of another is necessary strategies. Less promotion and more understanding. Setting the goal of receiving of the final click, it is necessary to communicate on at the personal level, acceptance of the person with whom you communicate with whom you are serious about, communicate in her language. That's why, besides smart technology is the future of marketing communications is impossible without smart and creative storytellers, talented visualizers, who with their works are able to reach the consumer's subconscious and feelings.

Despite the huge progress in all spheres of modern life, human nature, in general, remained unchanged: a person seeks live contact, has a high level of empathy, wants to understand and be understood and still trusts own instincts: touch, sight, hearing, taste, smell [3].

Discounts, various promotions and incentives in the purchase process, Black Fridays and Cyber Mondays – these days you can't surprise anyone with them, they are everywhere. And it's not about the stories brands that cannot be refused. It's a matter of emotional willingness to pay attention Of course, interesting offers can strengthen the appeal of the brand, but it is not possible to strengthen what is not there.

Summarizing the above trends and perspective directions of world development advertising market, it is worth highlighting the key communication trends specifically for Ukraine in the coming years. Undoubtedly, Ukrainian marketing is increasingly integrated to the global market, so in the coming years we will be able to observe at the local level, the manifestation of global communication trends in various interpretations and adaptations.

Perspective directions of further research. The war exposed the advertising business. A whole new market and awareness of advertising is taking shape right now. Messages have changed. The consumer is not encouraged to buy with the last money or to please a loved one, but on the contrary, they explain why it is necessary to do it now and really add value to the product/product. The consumer has also become different. Today, the audience does not want to see fiction, but needs to reproduce the realities of business. Usually, pop commercials feature stars and heroes, but today they have changed. And, these are ordinary people – brave and indomitable.

Many events that took place in 2022 determined the vectors of our country's future movement. Since the beginning of March, the number of legislative innovations has been impressive – the state quickly learned to live in the regime of martial law. In particular, European integration processes were maximally intensified. Our country aspires to become a full member of the European Union. This path involves many changes and transformations that both our state and business must go through.

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